

Commentary on the ESMO Guidance for LLM Use in Oncology: Narrative and Process Divergences

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Main text

The recent ESMO guidance by Wong et al. on the use of large language models (LLMs) in oncology, based on an international Delphi process, offers a useful classification of application scenarios. We believe that a central methodological issue requires clarification: in several parts of the document, the narrative extends functions that the Delphi statements do not support, with implications for how clinicians may interpret it[1].

A consistent discrepancy emerges between the statements approved through the Delphi process and the way the same areas of use are presented in the narrative section. This is not a minor stylistic point: the gap alters what readers may consider appropriate in clinical practice.

In the section on patient-facing chatbots, the statement closest to the idea of a first point of consultation does not reach the required level of agreement. Nevertheless, the narrative attributes to these tools functions that correspond, in practice, to a first consult: symptom guidance, reduction of non-urgent visits, and support in moments of clinical uncertainty. This amounts to implicit triage and goes beyond what the Delphi approved.

In the section on tools for clinicians, the statements maintain a cautious profile limited to information retrieval and documentation synthesis. The narrative, however, introduces formulations that bring these systems closer to clinical decision support, including references to therapeutic suggestions and case-level “reasoning”. Here too, the scope described is broader than what emerged from the voting process.

Finally, regarding background AI systems, the only operational example cited by the authors is described in the original work as a tool restricted to documentation management and information organisation, with no role in decision making. In the guidance, the same system is presented as an illustration of broader LLM integration within clinical workflows. Once again, the narrative attributes implications that are not supported by the Delphi process or the underlying evidence.

The document repeatedly includes cautionary phrases calling for additional studies before adopting these scenarios. However, these clauses do not change the breadth of the functions attributed to LLMs in the narrative. The pattern is consistent: an expansive use case is proposed, followed immediately by a reminder of the need for validation. This results in a formal caution that does not limit readers' interpretation or realign the narrative with the Delphi statements.

The conclusion of the guidance introduces the concept of "shared responsibility" between clinicians and LLM-based systems. This formulation presupposes minimum properties of traceability and internal continuity[2]. Yet LLMs do not have persistent state, do not maintain a stable identity across interactions, and do not allow reconstruction of the steps leading to an output[3], all requirements that the EU AI Act mandates for high-risk medical AI systems[4]. Without state and without an audit trail, no proportion of responsibility can be meaningfully attributed to the system, clinically or regulatorily[2]. This applies even to seemingly safer scenarios, such as information support or documentation synthesis. The reference to shared responsibility therefore risks adding ambiguity and widening the gap already present between narrative and Delphi outcomes.

Our observations do not question the overall usefulness of the guidance but concern the internal coherence between the Delphi results, the narrative, and the technical limitations of the models. Clarifying these points could help readers interpret the document in line with the authors' intentions.

References

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